

*Resilient modulus of soils.*



Top Left. The complete equipment showing the mechanical parts and pneumatic cylinder

Top center. Special transparent chamber to simulate the surrounding soil pressure.

Top right. Electronic box and PC screen showing dynamic results.

Bottom left. LVDTs sensors and load cell.

Bottom right. Soil sample under test.

This machine applies a calibrated haversine wave form to a sample of soil and measures its deformation. In order to comply with standard AASHTO T-294-92 I, the testing machine has

the capability of applying the loads over a range of frequencies from 0.1 to 20 Hz and stress levels up to 100 psi. The force is generated by a pneumatic cylinder and a proportional flow solenoid valve.

The soil samples are subjected to different pressures to simulate the soil surrounding the sample. For this purpose a special transparent chamber was designed to apply the surrounding pressure simultaneously to the dynamic force. The longitudinal deformation of the sample is measured by two LVDT, force is measured with a load cell and pressure with a pressure sensor. The pressure is automatically varied during the test to emulate different soil compactions.

The electronics consisted of analog and digital circuits placed close to the chamber and connected to a PC. The PC is used to set the test parameters, results are shown on the PC screen and stored for analysis and reports.